

ANALYSIS OF MODELS OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE

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Annotation

The purpose of this research is to highlight the need to focus on communicative language teaching in the system of foreign language teaching, thereby analyzing the division of communicative competence into components, predicting the importance of the formation of communicative competence in professionals. One of the tasks of the scientific work was to study the analysis of communicative competence as a separate group of scientists through modeling method.

Keywords Competence, communicative competence, model, communicative language teaching, component, framework, socio-cultural competence, linguistic competence, discourse competence, strategic competence, gramatic competence, sociolinguistic competence.

Introduction

The term «communicative competence» is comprised of two words, the combination of which means «competence to communicate». This simple lexicosemantic analysis uncovers the fact that the central word in the syntagm «communicative competence» is the word «competence». And «Competence» is one of the most controversial terms in the field of general and applied linguistics. Its introduction to linguistic discourse has been generally associated with Chomsky who in his very influential book «Aspects of the Theory of Syntax» drew what has

been today viewed as a classic distinction between competence (the monolingual speaker-listener’s knowledge of language) and performance (the actual use of language in real situations)¹

Methods

In the research process, we used methods of analysis, synthesis and modeling (in order to reveal the importance of communicative language learning in the process of language teaching and to highlight the components of communicative competence). We also used the classification method (in order to highlight the internal components of the communicative competence introduced by the scientists), the system method (to collect research materials). Induction and deduction methods were also partially used.

The phrase “communicative competence” was first coined in 1967 by the American sociolinguist and anthropologist Dell H. Hymes in reaction to Chomsky’s notion of linguistic competence. He defines communicative competence as what “enables a member of the community to know when to speak and when to remain silent, which code to use, when, where and to whom, etc. (Hymes, 1967, p. 13). Since then, the concept has developed over years and different models of communicative competence have been offered by different scholars. Major models of communicative competence can be listed as follows:

Hymes’ model (1967, 1972); Canale and Swain’s model (1980); Canale (1983); Bachman’s model (1990); Celce-Murcia’s model (1995); Littlewood’s model (2011).

¹ According to many general and applied linguists, Chomsky’s distinction between competence and performance is based on the fundamental linguistic distinction between *langue* and *parole* which was made by de Saussure.

Results

In what follows, each of these models is described and in the rest of the paper, the implications of these models for language teachers and teacher educators are stated.

Hymes’ model of communicative competence

Before explaining the concept of communicative competence as presented by Hymes, the word “competence” itself requires some clarification. The word competence or linguistic competence was first used by Chomsky to refer to knowledge of language as different from performance which he sees as the actual use of language. Hymes (1972), while accepting the superiority of Chomsky’s terminology over de Saussure’s, contends: “Such a theory of competence posits ideal objects in abstraction from sociocultural features”.

A linguistically competent person, who is master of fully grammatical sentences, is at best a bit odd because “some occasions call for being appropriately ungrammatical” (p.277). Hymes adds, in addition to knowledge of grammatical sentences, a person should acquire the knowledge of appropriate sentences that is, he or she should know “when to speak, when not, and as to what to talk about with whom, when; where, in what manner”. He continues, “There are rules of use without which the rules of grammar would be useless”. Grammatical competence described by Chomsky, Hymes believes (see figure 1), is only one sector of communicative competence, the other ones mentioned by Hymes are the psycholinguistic (i.e., implementational feasibility), sociocultural (contextual appropriateness) and de facto (i.e., actual occurrence) sectors. In summarizing

Hymes’ model, Munby (1978) maintains the goal of the model is “to show the ways in which the systematically possible, the feasible, and the appropriate are linked to produce and interpret actually occurring cultural behavior”.

Figure 1. Hymes's model of communicative competence

A normal learner acquires knowledge of sentences not only grammatical, but also as appropriate. (Hymes,1972)

According to Hymes frame there are four main components of communicative competence. They are linguistic competence, discourse competence, sociolinguistic competence and strategic competence. Linguistic competence is the knowledge of the language code, its grammar and vocabulary, and also of the conversations of its written representation. Sociolinguistic competence is the knowledge of socio-cultural rules of use, i.e. knowing how to use and respond to language appropriately. Discourse competence is the knowledge of how to produce and comprehend oral or written texts in the modes of speaking/reading respectively. It's knowing how to combine language structures into a cohesive and coherent oral and written text of different types. Strategic competence is the ability to recognize and repair communication breakdowns before, during, or after they occur. Hymes developed a valuable model to assist the identification and labeling of components of linguistic interaction that was driven by his view that, in order to speak a language correctly,

one needs not only to learn its vocabulary and grammar, but also the context in which words are used.

Canale and Swain’s model of communicative competence

Another model of communicative competence was presented by the two Canadian applied linguists, Michael Canale and Merrill Swain in 1980 in the first issue of Applied Linguistics. Referring to the weak or neural and strong versions of Chomsky’s competence recognized by Campbell and Wales, Canale and Swain agree with Hymes’ criticism of Chomsky’s notion of competence –performance distinction in that it “provides no place for consideration of the appropriateness[emphasis is original] of socio-cultural significance of an utterance in the situational and verbal context in which it is used” (Howatt, 1986, p.4). Furthermore, referring to two views regarding the relationship between grammatical competence and communicative competence, they advocate Munby’s stance which sees grammatical competence a subpart of communicative competence and not something separate from it. They emphasize: “Just as Hymes was able to say that there are rules of grammar that would be useless without rules of language use, so we feel that there are rules of language use that would be useless without rules of grammar” (Hymes,1972). However, they do not incorporate the notion of ability for use into their definition of communicative competence

Reviewing theories of basic communication skills, sociolinguistic perspectives on communicative competence, and integrative theories of communicative competence.

Canale’s model of communicative competence

Three years after the communicative competence model proposed by Canale and Swain, Canale, based on the work carried out at the Ontario Institute for Studies in Education, revised the model and proposed a four-component framework. Prior to introducing his new model, Canale reminds the reader that in the communicative competence model, communication is meant to be “the exchange and negotiation²

² Negotiation is term that is formal discussion between people who are trying to reach an argument

of information between at least two individuals through the use of verbal and non-verbal symbols, oral and written/visual modes, and production and comprehension processes” (Hymes,1972). The four components of the revised framework are grammatical competence, sociolinguistic competence, discourse competence and strategic competence.

Grammatical competence, as in the previous model, is concerned with “features and rules of the language such as vocabulary, word formation, sentence formation, pronunciation, spelling and linguistic semantics” (Hymes,1972). Sociolinguistic competence in this model, unlike the Canale and Swain’s model, which addressed both socio-cultural rules and rules of discourse, “addresses the extent to which utterances are produced and understood appropriately in different sociolinguistic contexts depending on contextual factors such as status of participants, purposes of the interaction, and norms or conventions of interaction” (Hymes,1972), appropriateness of both form and meaning. Appropriateness of meaning also includes kinesics and proxemics. Canale believes this theoretical framework (see fig.2) is not a model of communicative competence, because a model “implies some specification of the manner and order in which the components interact and in which the various competences are normally acquired” (Hymes,1972,p.12).

Figure 2. According to Canale and Swain's model, components of Communicative competence.

Bachman's model of communicative competence

Another model of communicative competence or a “theoretical framework of communicative language ability” as he puts it, is the one proposed by Bachman, which has been presented for measurement purposes. This framework includes three components of language competence, strategic competence, and psychophysiological mechanisms. Language competence includes organizational and pragmatic competences. Organizational competence, in turn includes grammatical and textual abilities or competences, which are involved in producing and comprehending language. In other words, textual competence corresponds to discourse competence in Canale's model. Pragmatic competence is concerned with “the relationship between utterances and the acts or functions that speakers (or writers) intend to perform through these utterances” (Bachman, 1990, p. 89).

Pragmatic competence in Bachman's model encompasses illocutionary competence and sociolinguistic competence. Illocutionary competence entails knowledge and skill in using language functions proposed by Halliday such as ideational, manipulative, heuristic, instrumental, regulatory and imaginative functions. The second major component of communicative competence in Bachman's framework is strategic competence. Unlike Canale and Swain's and Canale's model, where strategic competence is at the same level as grammatical and sociolinguistic competences, in Bachman's model, strategic competence is a major component at the same level as language competence. The reason, as Bachman states, is that previous models imply that communicative strategies are necessarily linguistic or verbal ones but his model shows that strategic competence is a competence at the level of language competence not a subpart so it may include strategies which are not linguistic. Moreover, he believes strategic competence is “an important part of all communicative language use, not just that in which

language abilities are deficient and must be compensated for by other means” (Bachman, 1990, p. 100)

Celce-Murcia’s model of communicative competence

One of the important contributions of Celce-Murcia et al. (Murcia.1995) was to specify that the various components of communicative competence were interrelated and that it was important to properly describe the nature of these interrelationships in order to fully understand the construct of communicative competence. To this end they offered in their 1995 publication, which made the interrelationships explicit: This 1995 model is a pyramid enclosing a circle, surrounded by another circle. The circle inside the pyramid is discourse competence, the core or central competence. The three points of the triangle³ are the top-down socio-cultural competence and the bottom-up linguistic competence and actional competence.

Littlewood’s model of communicative competence

The final and the most recent framework or model of communicative competence reviewed here is the one presented by Littlewood (2011). He also takes Canale and Swains’ (1980) and Canale’s (1983) model as the initial model and develops it by adding a fifth component as well as adapting the terminology. The components of communicative competence in Littlewood’s model are as follows: linguistic competence, discourse competence, pragmatic competence, sociolinguistic, sociocultural. This last component introduces psycholinguistic aspects of second language proficiency that are not included in the Canale and Swain's framework but are fundamental to communicative language use.

Data collection and Analysis

The first scientific work on communicative competence was conducted by Chomsky, he perfected his scientific work from 1957 to 1965 and based his opinion

³ Three straight sides of communicative competence

on facts and examples. Hymes, Canale, and Swain later used this of his scientific research and divided it into components of communicative competence. In the 1990s, Bachman also worked on Communicative Competence, but his work was slightly different from models of Canale and Swain. Bachman also proved them with his substantial components. Five years after Bachman’s work, American professor Celce-Murcia worked on Communicative Competence, introducing Actional Competence as a separate component in addition to Canale’s Communicative Model. By 2011, Littlewood Communicative had perfected its competence. That is, earlier scholars included "socio-cultural competence" in the internal structure of "Sociolinguistic competence". However, Littlewood singles out “Socio-Cultural Competence” as a particularly important competency, describing it as the most fundamental component of communicative competence. (figure 3) That is, over the years, communicative competence has been brought to perfection, and its components have increased. Indeed, in today’s era based on Independent Dialogue, socio-cultural competence is crucial.

Figure 3. Evolution of Communicative Competence's Models

Discussion and Conclusion

One of the essential competencies for foreign language teachers is communicative competence. Communicative competence is the main pillar of communication, fluency in the language being studied, and it plays a key role in communicating freely with speakers of the language as a true mother tongue, and communication is also important in foreign language teaching. It is widely used in the correction of deficiencies in foreign language learners. Many scholars have worked on and expressed their views on communicative competence, and they have also divided this competence into components. Common feature of these models of communicative competence is that they all include a discourse or textual component. This textual or discourse component implies that in a Communicative Language Teaching teacher should have the ability to produce and comprehend cohesive and coherent texts both oral and written and should help his students to develop such a competence too.

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